

AN ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC DETERMINANTS OF DOMESTIC FOOD PRODUCTION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined economic determinants of domestic food production in Nigeria. It used of secondary data which were drawn from various sources including Food and Agriculture Statistical Facts, Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, World Hunger Index. The data spanned between 1981 and 2021. Descriptive and econometric (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) methods were employed for data analysis. Findings showed that in Nigeria, arable land, exchange rate, and food imports significantly affected domestic food production. It is, therefore, recommended that the vast uncultivated arable land be cultivated for more domestic food production to match the food need of the increasing population and to reduce food imports. Also, production of domestic agricultural inputs should be encouraged through the development of appropriate technology. This will bring about increase in domestic agricultural inputs, and consequent decrease in importation of agricultural inputs, thus reducing the influence of exchange rate on agricultural production.

KEYWORDS: Domestic Food Production, Food Import, Economic Determinants, and Undernourishment

INTRODUCTION

Food is the most essential and basic need of all humans. Provision of adequate quantity and quality of food, therefore, is one goal every country seeks to achieve and to stain. This is one reason every country pursues veritable agricultural programmes to achieve

adequate food production. In Nigeria, from early 1970s to the present, various food production programmes have been adopted by successive governments to boost food production so as to balance food demand with food supply. Such programmes included Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs) adopted in 1972, with the aim of increasing agricultural productivity, increasing incomes of farmers and raising the standard of living of the people, especially rural dwellers (Ojo, 1991). In 1974, the government established the National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFFP) which aimed at accelerating the rate of food production and reducing food imports. National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFFP) was in operation for only two years, and within this short period, it could not achieve its broad objectives. In 1976, NAFFP was replaced with Operations Feed the Nation (OFN), which aimed at producing enough food to feed the nation. In the same year, 1976, River Basin Development Authority (RBDA) was established with the aim to “regenerate rural agriculture, provide modern farm settlements with basic amenities such as electricity and water supply, create congenial environment in rural areas to discourage farm labour from migrating to urban centres” (Ekong, 1997). River Basin Development Authority (RBDA), which is still in operation, is yet to optimally deliver on its lofty objectives.

In 1980, the Green Revolution was adopted with the aim of revolutionizing agriculture in Nigeria. After six years, Directorate for Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI) was established in 1986 to increase food production and reduce rural poverty. In 1990s, National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA) and National Fadama Development Project (NFDP) were adopted. The National Fadama Development Project was initiated to address some of the factors that militated against full realization of the benefits of agricultural production activities in some areas. Some of these factors were poor development of rural infrastructure, low investment in irrigation technology, poor organization of Fadama farmers, and limited access to foreign exchange for importation of irrigation equipment (CBN, 2010: 145). In 1998, National Special Programme on Food security (NSPFS) was adopted. This programme was jointly sponsored by the Federal Government and Food and Agricultural Organization, and was designed to be executed over a five-year period at the cost of US\$ 45.2 million. The broad objective of NSPFS was to attain food security for the country. The National Special Programme on Food security (NSPFS) was supported by Root and Tuber Expansion Programme (RTEP) which was launched in 2003 to tackle the inadequate food situation in the country. Between 2011 and 2022, the government adopted various food production programmes such as National Food Security Programme (NFSP) and the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), with a view to radically change Nigeria's agriculture, and rejuvenate the sector for improved food production.

However, global report of assessment of food situations in countries in the last decade placed Nigeria among food-insufficient countries in the world. As reported by IFPRI (2016) and FAO (2017) between 2014 and 2016, the number of people undernourished in Nigeria increased to an estimated 14.3 million, up from 10.2 million between 2010 and 2012. The number of people undernourished increased to 23.9 million between 2017 and 2019, while the number of severely food insecure people between 2014 and 2016 was estimated at 44.6 million, the highest in West Africa. The situation of food inadequacy in Nigeria placed the country in 90th position, with a score of 32% in a pool of 133 countries in global food security ranking by FAO in 2016 (FAO, 2017). In 2022, in Global Food Security assessment/ranking,

12.7% of population in Nigeria was undernourished, with 35.3% children stunted (IFPRI, 2022). This assessment placed Nigeria in 107th position, with a score of 42.0%, in a poll of 133 countries. This indicates that food supply in Nigeria is insufficient and inadequate. Food supply in any country comes from two main sources – local food production and food imports. From the literature, both domestic food production and food imports are determined by some factors. The objective of this study is to analyze economic determinants of domestic food production in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

Theoretical Literature

Malthusian Theory of Population and Food Supply

Thomas Robert Malthus (1766 – 1834) was the first to address food scarcity as an issue in relation to growth in human population in relatively recent time. He developed his views on population in relation to food supply to contradict his father's perfectionist opinion that the human race was always improving (Samuelson and Nordhaus, 2010). In his work, “An Essay on the Principle of Production, as it affects the future improvement of society”, (Malthus, 1798) pointed that the growth of population is ultimately limited by the food supply. In other words, he postulated that population, when allowed to increase without limit, increases in a geometrical ratio while the food supply can, at least, increase in an arithmetical ratio, thus, making it impossible for agricultural production to sustain growing population indefinitely. Malthus (1798), therefore, hypothesized that “The power of population is indefinitely greater than the power in the earth to produce subsistence for man (Samuelson and Nordhaus, *ibid*). That is, growing global population will eventually eclipse the earth's capacity to feed it. The Malthusian theory of population growth in relation to food supply was based on the law of diminishing returns which explains that output from farm land would decrease as more and more of the poorer lands were brought into cultivation (even repeatedly) as a result of population pressure.

Malthus, in Blaug (1986), maintained that “Whatever the plausible rate of increase of the food requirements, an unchecked multiplication of human beings would quickly lead to standing room only”. It seemed obvious to him that something had to keep the population in check to prevent wholesome starvation. He said that there were two general kinds of checks that limit population growth - preventative checks and positive checks. Preventative checks reduce the birth rate while positive checks increase the death rate. In other words, he labelled preventive checks as “manifestations of vice”, which could be achieved through abortion and infanticide, which hold down the birth rate, while the positive checks he labelled as “manifestations of misery”, and can be achieved through war, famine, pestilence, etc., which increase death rate. He further asserted that population could be checked by “moral restraint”, meaning postponement of the age of marriage accompanied by strict-sexual abstinence before marriage and sexual restraint by married couples (Blaug, *Ibid*).

Malthusian Population Theory over the years has instigated intense arguments; while some scholars, demographers and development analysts are in support of the theory, some are in disagreement and of differing views.

Qays's Theory of Food Supply

Qays's theory of food supply is also known as theory of agricultural intensification. It was developed by Ester Boserup in 1965. Qays's theory is about the relationship between human population growth and food production. Boserup (1965), in her work "The conditions of agricultural growth: The Economics of agrarian change under population pressure" challenged Malthus' conclusion that the size of the human population is limited by the amount of food it can produce. Qays's theory in contrast states that "food production can and will increase to match the needs of the population". For instance, where population grows rapidly, the theory argues that the threat of starvation and the challenge of feeding more mouths will motivate people to improve their farming methods and invent new technologies in order to produce more food. Boserup (1965) described this as "agricultural intensification. According to Qays's theory, a farmer who has four fields to cultivate and produce food for his family might cultivate three of the fields, and leave the fourth field empty probably due to the ground being very dry, and would not support his crops. However, if the farmer has two more children, the pressure to produce more food might drive him to build irrigation canal to bring water to the fourth field or to buy a different type of seed that will grow in drier ground. He certainly would change the way he farms so as to make sure that he has enough food to support a large family (Boserup, 1965).

Boserup's theory seems to provide a model for continuous population growth. Boserup (1965) failed to consider that growth in human population is continuous, while agricultural land is static. The theory ignored the aspect of population density, increased urbanization and erosion which reduce the size of crop land yearly. According to Pimentel, Huang, Cordova and Pimentel (1997), about 33 per cent or 1.5 billion hectares of world crop land has been abandoned due to erosion. They attributed global food shortage to lower land productivity, which is as a result of continuous environmental degradation.

Empirical Literature

Credible evidences that point to the growing imbalance between demand for food and supply of food, especially in less-developed countries abound. Babatunde and Ajayi (2010) sought to investigate the relationship between population growth and production of selected food crops (maize, rice, beans, plantain, yam, cassava and groundnut) in rural areas in Western Nigeria. They adopted ordinary least square estimation. Results revealed an inverse relationship between population growth and growth of each of the food crops. That is, as population in rural areas increase, production of the food crops considered rather decreased. They attributed this to relegation of agriculture by many rural youths who migrate to urban areas in search of white-collar jobs. They recommended rapid government intervention in rural development and rural agriculture, as rural areas are the prime food producers in Nigeria.

Maisonet-Guzman (2011) observed that area of land dedicated to agriculture plays a central role in determining a countries agricultural production. However, some countries, especially in Africa, with vast areas of land dedicated to agriculture still experience low agricultural production due to poor and low level of modern technology. Recommendation, therefore, was that such countries should invest more in modern agricultural technology to increase agricultural production. Ojo and Adebayo (2012) assessed the state of food sufficiency in Nigeria by reviewing Nigeria's agricultural policies and programmes between 2000 and 2012. They observed that some agricultural policies and programmes adopted in

Nigeria though ideally sound were haphazardly implemented. They argued that there is a wide gap between agricultural policies and agricultural practices in Nigeria. Thus, they attributed the food scarcity in Nigeria largely to poor implementation of agricultural policies. They recommended agricultural policies that match agricultural practices in Nigeria.

Abdulrahman (2013) investigated the relationship between population growth and food security using agricultural production as a proxy for food security. He used Ordinary Least Square (OLS) in model estimation and data analysis. Findings revealed that food insecurity in Nigeria is largely due to rapid population growth which outmatches food production, as such, established family planning measures should be adopted to check the rapid population growth. Di-Marcantonio, *et al.*, (2014) carried out a study to investigate the determinants of food production in sub-Saharan Africa. They adopted a macro approach, with country level data for 41 sub-Saharan countries obtained from Food and Agriculture Organization Statics (FAOSTAT) and individual country data set. Their independent variables included agricultural land, irrigation, agriculture labour, inflation, conflicts, and number of tractors, food aid agricultural research, and governance. They used panel data regression technique with fixed and random effects for model estimation and analysis. Findings from their study showed, among others, that food production is usually and substantially low in landlocked countries and countries with prolonged conflicts. They also found out that food aid related negatively but significantly with local food production, while agricultural research related positively and significantly with local food production. They strongly recommended congenial macroeconomic environment and good governance with minimal conflict. For landlocked countries, with very low agricultural production, they recommended adequate technology transfer from the industrialized countries.

Anigbogu, *et al.*, (2015) sought to investigate the reasons the growth in food production and population growth are out of balance. Specifically, they sought to examine the socio-economic factors responsible for food production among cooperative farmers in Anambra state of Nigeria. They selected their sample and gathered their data by survey. Precisely, they adopted multi-stage sampling techniques to determine the sample size of their study from the three senatorial districts of the state. Two local governments were randomly selected from each senatorial district. Two towns were then selected from each local government; and from each town, two farmers cooperatives were randomly selected. The twenty-four farmers cooperatives selected comprised of 171 farmers to whom 171 copies of the questionnaire were administered out of which, 142 copies were completed and returned. The ordinary least square technique was what they used for model estimation and data analysis. The variables they considered included outputs of farmers, sizes of households, credit obtained by farmers, quantities of fertilizers, incomes of farmers, type of technology, soil fertility, sex, age, and educational qualification of farmers. All the variables, from the findings, related positively with farmers' output except sex and age, which related negatively. They recommended, among others, improvements in the provision of credits to cooperative farmers, by the government and financial institutions, to aid in the expansion of their farm activities. Also, to address the problem of shortage in agricultural labour, young graduates should be encouraged and incentivized to involve in agricultural activities

Matemilola and Elegbede (2017) investigated the challenges of food production in Nigeria using a descriptive approach. They assessed Nigeria's food production status prior to and after the discovery of oil up to 2016. In the findings, they observed that prior to the

discovery of oil in Nigeria in commercial quantity; Nigeria was food secure as the agricultural sector was given considerable regard and adequate attention, which enabled the sector to produce enough food to feed its population. However, since the discovery of oil, the agricultural sector has been relegated and, consequently its productivity has been decreasing. Also, they argued from the findings that of about 75 percent of Nigeria's land suitable agriculture, only 40 percent is actually cultivated. They identified the causes (challenges) of food security in Nigeria to include increasing population, decreasing per capita arable land, inadequate supply and deplorable state of infrastructure, inefficient agricultural policies, conflicts and civil insecurity, oil spillage, low level of technology in processing and storage of agricultural products. To bring Nigeria out of its food insecurity situation, they recommended adequate provision of basic infrastructure in rural communities, access roads, electricity, proper control of oil spillage, which negatively affects some farmlands and aquatic lives, improvement and adoption of congruent science and technology in processing and storage of agricultural produce.

Similarly, in 2018, Khan, *et al.*, sought to examine the key socio-economic determinants of food security in Jhang, one of the largest districts in Punjab, Pakistan. They adopted survey method and applied proportionate random sampling technique to select 200 households from whom data were drawn through questionnaire administration. In their study, per capita calorie intake was a proxy for food security, while independent variables of interest included age, sex, and education status of household heads, family size, and tenancy status, total earning hands, number of domestic animals, floods, and drought. Logit regression technique was used for data analysis. Findings showed that total earning hands, sex and education status of household, tenancy status determined the odds of being food secure, while total number of animals, floods, family size, draught and age of household head determined the odds of being food insecure. They recommended, among others, family planning through awareness campaigns use of modern technology in weather forecast to give timely information to farmer about some adverse, natural occurrences.

Similarly, Mota, *et al.*, (2019) assessed the determinants of food insecurity in rural households in Damot Gale Woreda, Wolaita zone of Southern Ethiopia. They used survey approach in which 155 households were randomly selected. They used logit regression technique for data analysis. The findings based on the Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAC), revealed that about 71.6 percent of rural households in Damot Gale Woreda were food insecure. Large family size, low income, and fragmented farm lands were among the major determinants of food insecurity in the study area. They recommended family planning and income-generating activities to help rural households to be food secure.

Nigeria's Domestic Food Production: Agricultural Sector Performance

We will assess the performance of Nigeria's agricultural sector using share of agricultural output to gross domestic product, annual growth rate of agricultural production and growth in major crop production. Table 3.1 mirrors total real GDP, agriculture's contributions and the growth rates of the contributions.

Table 1: Contribution of Agriculture to GDP at 2010 Constant Basic Prices, GDP, (N Billion), 1990 – 2021 Year

Year (1)	Total GDP (2)	Share of Agriculture in Total GDP (3)	Share of Agriculture as % GDP (4)	Growth rate of Agricultural GDP (5)
1990	19,705.63	3,463.72	17.58	4.14
1991	19,194.38	3,590.84	18.71	3.67
1992	19,620.29	3,674.79	18.73	2.34
1993	19,927.39	3,748.47	18.81	2.01
1994	19,979.12	3,839.46	19.22	2.43
1995	20,353.28	3,977.48	19.54	3.59
1996	21,177.32	4,131.55	19.51	3.87
1997	21,782.10	4,305.68	19.77	4.21
1998	22,332.87	4,475.24	20.04	3.94
1999	22,449.42	4,705.64	20.96	5.15
2000	22,688.23	4,840.87	21.34	2.87
2001	25,267.54	5,024.54	19.89	3.79
2002	28,967.71	7,817.38	26.99	55.58
2003	31,709.46	8,364.83	26.38	7.00
2004	35,020.55	8,388.57	23.95	0.28
2005	37,474.95	9,516.99	25.40	13.45
2006	39,995.50	10,222.47	25.56	7.41
2007	42,922.41	10,695.47	24.92	4.63
2008	46,012.52	11,645.37	25.31	8.88
2009	49,856.10	12,330.33	24.73	5.88
2010	54,612.26	13,068.89	23.93	5.99
2011	57,511.04	13,439.38	23.37	2.83
2012	59,929.89	14,329.71	23.91	6.62
2013	63,218.72	14,750.52	23.33	2.94
2014	67,152.70	15,380.29	22.90	4.27
2015	69,022.03	15,052.22	21.81	- 2.13
2016	67,531.36	16,407.34	24.30	9.00
2017	68,499.90	17,179.80	25.08	4.71
2018	69,815.02	17,544.15	25.13	2.12
2019	71,387.83	17,958.58	25.16	2.36
2020	70,014.37	18,348.18	26.21	2.17
2021	72,393.67	18,738.41	23.88	2.13

Sources: Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) *Statistical Bulletin*, 2018: 111 – 112; 2022
Note: Columns 4 and 5 calculated by the authors from columns 2 and 3.

From Table 1, in 1990, real GDP was N19, 705.63 billion with agriculture's share of N3, 463.72 billion (17.58 %). Real GDP rose to N20, 353.28 billion with N3, 977.48 billion (19.54 %) as value added from agriculture. In 2002, real GDP reached N28, 907.71 billion to which agriculture contributed N7, 817.38 billion (26.99 %). In 2004, real GDP was N35, 020.55 billion, and agriculture contributed N8, 388.57 (23.95 %), 3.04 % less its contribution in 2002. In 2015, real GDP was N69, 022.03 billion, with N15, 052.22 billion (21.81 %) from agriculture. In 2018, real GDP was N69, 815.02 billion; agriculture contributed N17, 544.15 billion (25.13 %). In 2021, GDP was N72,393.67 billion, with N18,738.41 (23.88%) from agriculture.

Between 1998 and 2001, growth rates of GDP of agriculture were positive. In 2002, it increased by 55 .58 %. Thereafter, it grew by 0.28 in 2005. Between 2009 and 2014, growth rates of GDP of agriculture were all positive but less 7 %. In 2015, it grew by – 2.13 %. In 2016, agriculture GDP grew by 9.00 %, and in 2017, it grew by 4.17 %. In 2018, share of agriculture to GDP grew by 2.12 %. In 2021, share of agriculture in GDP grew by 2.13%. Between 1990 and 2021, the period under review, growth rates of agriculture GDP fluctuated. The swings in growth rates of agriculture GDP indicate the undeveloped state of the agricultural sector in Nigeria, and that the sector is not self-sufficient in food production.

A consideration of growth in major crop production also portrays the performance agricultural sector in Nigeria. Growths in major crop production in recent past have not been impressive. Table 2 presents growth in major crop production in Nigeria between 2010 and 2018.

Table 2: Growth in major crop production

Crops	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Beans	6.1	6.5	4.2	3.2	1.7	4.3	2.2	1.1	2.2
Cassava	6.9	6.0	2.2	3.8	4.4	3.9	3.7	2.0	1.9
Cocoa	6.6	8.3	3.4	4.7	3.4	3.3	3.2	3.3	3.5
Maize	5.9	6.5	2.8	3.7	1.2	1.4	4.4	0.7	0.4
Millet	4.9	5.2	1.2	2.6	1.1	0.7	0.6	0.4	1.9
Palm oil	8.3	9.7	3.3	2.2	4.1	4.0	3.8	3.6	2.2
Plantain	5.5	6.5	2.7	2.1	2.6	4.4	2.5	2.0	3.5
Potatoes	5.8	6.8	4.1	4.0	3.1	4.5	3.2	1.3	2.0
Rice	4.0	5.0	2.4	4.0	4.1	4.0	3.7	2.6	5.4
Sorghum	4.0	5.4	3.1	3.3	1.3	4.1	5.5	1.8	2.0
Soya-beans	8.4	8.6	3.8	4.5	3.3	3.2	3.2	3.6	7.9
Wheat	5.5	6.3	2.6	2.3	2.6	2.4	5.5	2.2	3.3
Yam	4.8	5.4	1.4	3.4	0.1	3.8	1.6	0.3	2.9

Sources: Compiled from:

1. Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) *Annual Report*, 2011, p.129
2. Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) *Annual Report*, 2014, p.141
3. Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) *Annual Report*, 2016, p.193
4. Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) *Annual Report*, 2019, p.183

From Table 2, growth in beans production was 6.1 % in 2010 and 6.5 % in 2011. In 2016, beans production grew by 1.1 %, and in 2017 it grew by 1.1 %. It grew by 2.2 % in 2018. Cassava production grew by 6.9 % and 6.0 % in 2010 and 2011, respectively. In 2017 growth in cassava production was 2.0 % and 1.9 % in 2018. In the same vein, cocoa production which grew by 6.6 % and 8.3 %, in 2010 and 2011, respectively, reduced to 3.3 % in 2017, and rose marginally to 3.5 % in 2018. In 2010 and 2011, maize production in Nigeria grew by 5.9 % and 6.5 %, respectively. In 2017, growth in maize production reduced to 0.7 %. It further reduced to 0.4 % in 2018. Growth in production of potatoes was 5.8 % in 2010, and rose to 6.8 % in 2011. In 2017 it reduced to 1.3 %, and grew marginally to 2.0 % in 2018. Wheat production grew by 5.5 % in 2010. It increased to 6.3 % in 2011. It reduced to 2.2 % in 2017, then rose slightly to 3.3 % in 2018. In the same direction of wheat production, palm oil production grew by 8.3 % in 2010 and increased to 9.7 % in 2011. It reduced to 3.6 % in 2017 and further to 2.2 % in 2018. Production of yam has also reduced. In 2010, yam production grew by 4.8 %, and increased to 6.3 % in 2011. It reduced to 1.6 % in 2016 and further to 0.3 % in 2017. It marginally grew by 2.9 % in 2018. Rice production increased by 4.0 % in 2010, in 2011 it grew by 5.0 %. In 2012 and 2017, growth in rice production in Nigeria reduced to 2.4 % and 2.6%, respectively. However, it rose by 5.4 % in 2018. Soya-beans production in 2010 increased by 8.4 % in 2010 and increased to 8.6 % in 2011. Thereafter, it reduced to 3.8 % in 2012 and further to 3.2 % in 2015 and maintained same in 2016. It grew sluggishly by 3.6 %. In 2018 Soya-beans production increased by 7.9 %. From the above analysis, there has been a general decrease in the growth of domestic production of major crops in Nigeria for some years now.

METHODOLOGY

The objective of this study is to examine the determinants domestic food production in Nigeria. Based on this objective, the functional relationship is specified as in Equation 1

$$\text{Equation 1: } AGDP = f(AL, EXR, GEA, POP, IR, CPI)$$

where: AL is arable land, GEA is government expenditure on agriculture, POP is population, IR is interest rate, EXR is exchange rate, and CPI is consumer price index.

For econometric analysis, equation 1 is stated in a linear form as in Equation 2.

$$\text{Equation 2: } AGDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 AL + \alpha_2 EXR + \alpha_3 GEA + \alpha_4 POP + \alpha_5 IR + \alpha_6 CPI + U$$

Where α_0 is the intercept of the model, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5$ and α_6 are slope coefficients (that is, partial elasticities of agricultural output to percentage of arable land (AL), exchange rate (EXR), government expenditure on agriculture (GEA), population (POP), interest rate (IR) and consumer price index (CPI), respectively. A priori, in equation (3.4), the independent variables were expected to assume either positive or negative values depending on their relationship with the dependent variable. Thus, $\alpha_1, \alpha_3, \alpha_4 > 0$; $\alpha_2, \alpha_5, \alpha_6 < 0$, and U is the error term, which captures other variables which may affect agricultural output in Nigeria but not taken into account explicitly in the model.

The study used time series data from secondary sources - the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin (various issues), Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) Statistical Facts, Food Security Indicators, National Population Commission Official Gazette (1991 and 2006), World Development Indicators (WDI) (various issues), World Development

Reports (WDR) (various issues), Global hunger index, State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World, World Food Programme.

The study adopted the Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method for model estimation and analysis, since the data for the study were stationary at both 1(0) and 1(1), from the stationarity test. Moreover, the ARDL has its inbuilt error correction mechanism. It permits variables to have different optimal lags, and allows for simultaneous estimation of the long-run and short-run coefficients of the model as the error correction term is taken care of by the lagged period. With appropriate number of lags, ARDL addresses the problem of auto correlation and endogeneity (Parasan, *et al.*, 2001).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Unit Root Test

The Kwiatkowski – Phillips – Schimdt - Shin and Ng – Perron tests for unit root were adopted. The results are reported in the table below

Table 3: Unit root test results

Kwiatkowski – Phillips – Schimdt – Shin Test				Ng – Perron tests		
Variab les	Level	CV 1 %	Order of Integration	Level	CV 5%	Order of Integration
AGDP	0.6707***	0.7390	1(0)	-6.4193***	-2.5800	1(0)
AL	0.5879***	0.7390	1(0)	-2.9694***	-2.5800	1(1)
CPI	0.6845***	0.7390	1(0)	-10.4688***	-2.5800	1(1)
EXR	0.4157***	0.7390	1(1)	-2.8509***	-2.5800	1(1)
GEA	0.7185***	0.7390	1(0)	-3.9474***	-2.5800	1(1)
IR	0.1793***	0.7390	1(1)	-3.0095***	-2.5800	1(1)
POP	0.4631***	0.7390	1(1)	-6.6298***	-2.5800	1(0)

Source: Authors' computation from E-views 10.0

*** indicates stationarity at 1 percent level of significance

** indicates stationarity at 5 percent level of significance

The unit root test results in Table 3 show that our variables are stationary at level, 1(0) and first difference 1(1) at 1 % and 5 % levels of significance. The mixed order of integration necessitated the use of ARDL approach for estimation.

ARDL Bound Test Result

The result of the bound test is reported in Table 4.

Table 4: Bound Test Results

Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	15.60085	10%	1.99	2.94
K	6	5%	2.27	3.28
		2.5%	2.55	3.61
		1%	2.88	3.99

Source: Authors' computation from E-views 10.

As Table 4 shows, our calculated F-statistic of 15.6 is greater than the lower and upper bounds values of 2.27 and 3.28 respectively at 5% percent level of significance. This implies that there is a long run cointegrating relationship among the variables in the model.

Model Selection Criteria

Next, we subjected our model to lag length selection. This ensures that information about the relationship is not lost to inappropriate lag specification. Relying on Akaike information criteria for lag selection the lag specification of: ARDL (2, 3, 3, 0, 3, 2, 2) was Selected for the analysis and reported on Figure 1

Figure 1: Model Selection

Source: Authors' computation from E-views 10.0

Short run relationship between AGDP and its determinants

Table 5: Short Run Result
Dependent Variable: (AGDP)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
(AGDP(-1)	0.228863	0.084822	2.698159	0.0183
(AL)	-1.675785	0.302119	-5.546765	0.0001
(AL(-1)	1.486956	0.304576	4.882048	0.0003
(AL(-2)	0.489935	0.209848	2.334712	0.0362
(EXR)	-0.033803	0.033027	-1.023514	0.3247
(EXR(-1)	-0.495315	0.043119	-11.48707	0.0000
(EXR(-2),	-0.476556	0.039951	-11.92861	0.0000
(GEA)	0.044411	0.026930	1.694104	0.1231
(POP)	1.497416	3.568021	0.419677	0.6816
(POP(-1)	-4.676368	5.081512	-0.920271	0.3742
(POP(-2)	22.32625	3.557148	6.276445	0.0000
(IR)	-0.064459	0.082239	-0.783798	0.4472
(IR(-1)	0.268259	0.084396	3.178570	0.0073
(CPI)	1.166324	0.109884	10.61416	0.0000
(CPI(-1)	-0.695918	0.109864	-6.334385	0.0000
ECM (-1)	-1.323213	0.095492	-13.85678	0.0000
R-squared	0.951872	Mean dependent var		-0.002585
Adjusted R-squared	0.918182	S.D. dependent var		0.181090
S.E. of regression	0.051799	Akaike info criterion		-2.785378
Sum squared resid	0.053662	Schwarz criterion		-2.118801
Log likelihood	63.74412	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.555276
Durbin-Watson stat	1.948391			

Source: Authors' computation from E views 10.0

The agricultural production model shows economic factors that affect agricultural production in Nigeria within the period under review. The significant value of ECM - 1.32 shows the speed of adjustment of agricultural production (AGDP) to its past and present values, and past levels of AL, EXR, GEA, POP, IR AND CPI.

From Table 5, the coefficient of arable land is – 1.6757, which indicates that there is a negative relationship between arable land and AGDP in Nigeria. However, one-year lag of arable land (AL) showed positive and significant relationship with AGDP with a coefficient of 1.4869 which implies that a hectare increase in arable land would increase AGDP by N1.49 billion. Also, two-year lag of arable land (AL) showed positive and significant relationship with AGDP with a coefficient of 0.4899 which implies that a hectare increase in arable land would increase AGDP by N49 billion.

The coefficient of exchange rate is – 0.0338, which implies a negative relationship in the short run between exchange rate and AGDP. However, the relationship is insignificant. Nevertheless, past relationship between exchange rate and AGDP also shows negative but significant relationship at 5 % level of significance with coefficient of - 0.4953. This implies that a 1% decrease in the value of the naira relative to the dollar (US \$) would cause AGDP to decrease by about N49.5 billion. Government expenditure on agriculture (GEA) related

positively with agricultural GDP; however, the relationship was not significant at 5 % level of significance.

The coefficient of population is 1.4974. This indicates a positive relationship between population and agricultural output in Nigeria, that is, increase in population would lead to increase in agricultural output. However, the relationship was not significant. Nevertheless, two-year lag in population showed positive and significant relationship with agricultural output at 5 % with a coefficient of 22.3262. This implies that 1 % increase in population would increase AGDP by N22.33 billion. Interest rate with coefficient of -0.0645 related negatively with agricultural output. This implies that a percentage increase in interest rate would reduce AGDP by N6.5 billion. However, the relationship was not significant.

The relationship between Consumer price index (CPI) and agricultural GDP is positive and significant at 5 % level of significance with a coefficient of 1.1663. This implies that a 1 % increase in CPI would increase agricultural GDP lead to N1.17 billion.

The Durbin Watson Statistic of 1.95 shows that there is no serial correlation in the model. The adjusted R^2 of 0.9181 shows that about 92 % variation in the dependent variable (AGDP) is explained by the independent variables.

Long run Analysis between AGDP and its determinants

Table 6: Long Run Estimates

Dependent variable: AGDP

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
(AL)	-2.561288	0.684093	-3.744062	0.0025
(EXR)	0.397301	0.119248	3.331721	0.0054
(GEA)	0.033563	0.020852	1.609559	0.1315
(POP)	0.284403	2.600768	0.109353	0.9146
(IR)	-0.204423	0.247440	-0.826154	0.4236
(CPI)	0.821790	0.146949	5.592331	0.0001
C	0.018059	0.022790	0.792410	0.4423

Source: Authors' computation from E views 10.0

In the long run, from Table 6, the coefficient of arable land is -2.5613 . This implies that arable land has negative relationship with agricultural output, and the relationship is significant at 5 % level of significance.

In the long run, it is observed that exchange rate, that is, the rate at which the naira is exchanged for dollar, plays a positive and significant role in agricultural production in Nigeria with a coefficient of 0.3973. This implies that a percentage increase in exchange rate would increase AGDP by N39.7 billion

Government expenditure on agriculture (GEA) in the long run has a coefficient of 0.0336, which implies positive relationship with agricultural output; however, the relationship is not significant at 5 % level of significance. Population with a coefficient of 0.2844 also plays a positive role in agricultural production in Nigeria; however, the relationship is not significant at 5 % level of significance.

Interest rate in the long run has a coefficient of -0.2044 , which implies negative relationship with agricultural output. That is, a 1 % increase in interest rate would cause agricultural GDP to decrease by N20 billion. However, the relationship is insignificant. Consumer Price Index in the long run relates with agricultural GDP positively. Consumer Price Index, as we know is the measure of how the cost of purchasing a given basket of consumer good changes over time; so, as CPI increases, agricultural GDP also increases.

Stability results

The stability result of our model is reported in Figure 4.2. The cumulative sum of squares graph shows the parameter estimates fall within an acceptable confidence interval at 5 % level of significance. Therefore, the conclusions drawn from the results are reliable.

Figure 2: Stability results

Source: Authors' computation from E-views 10.0s

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The short run result exhibited negative and significant relationship between arable land and domestic food production in Nigeria which does not agree with a priori expectation. This may be attributed to increasing insecurity (herdsmen attacks on farmers) in many parts of the country. The attacks have, in recent times, caused some rural farmers to abandon their farmlands with consequent decrease in domestic food production. The one – year lag of exchange rate showed negative and significant relationship with domestic food production. This is because some agricultural inputs are imported and valued in dollar; and the value of the naira has been decreasing consistently relative to dollar. So, with the decreased value of the naira, less agricultural inputs would be imported, given the existing level of technology in agriculture in Nigeria, agricultural output will decrease. The two-year lag in population which showed positive and significant relationship with AGDP implies that, as population grows, demand for food would increase, and this would induce agricultural intensification with resultant growth in agricultural production nay food production. This agrees with Qays's theory of agricultural intensification by Busarup (1965) which argued that as population

increases, food production, through agricultural intensification, can and will increase to match the food needs of the people.

The long run negative and significant relationship between arable land and agricultural output was not in agreement with theoretical a priori expectation. Some probable factors might have caused the negative relationship given the Nigerian economy. Due to increased urbanization, there is a deterioration in the quality of marginal lands which leads to low productivity. In Nigeria, rural – urban migration is increasing, due to the quest for white-collar jobs, among other factors. Many people pursue formal education in order to secure formal employment either with the government or with the private sector. As we know arable land abound in the rural areas, so as rural-urban migration increases, agricultural labour in rural areas will decrease with consequent decrease in food production. In addition, our cultural perception of involvement in agriculture is discouraging as it is associated with third class (poor) citizens. This perception could make some rural youths who do not migrate to urban areas to dissociate themselves from agricultural activities. This again will reduce agricultural labour with consequent decrease in domestic food production. This, therefore, suggests that some part of arable land in the rural areas will be uncultivated, and this will lead to low agricultural production.

The long run positive and significant relationship between exchange rate and AGDP suggests that, given the long-time of consistent decrease in the value of the naira, that is, persistent increase in exchange rate and persistent rise in prices of food items, the prices at which agricultural products are sold in Nigeria support importation of agricultural inputs for more agricultural activities in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The determinants of domestic food production as specified in our Model were examined and the results showed that the key determinants of domestic food production in the short run were arable land (AL) and consumer price index (CPI). However, a one-period and a two-period lag in exchange rate showed negative but significant relationship with domestic food production. Also, a two-period lag in population showed positive and significant relationship with domestic food production. In the long run, the results showed that the key determinants of domestic food production were arable land (AL), exchange rate (EXR) and consumer price index (CPI). The Durbin Watson Statistic of 1.95 showed that there was on serial correlation in the model. The adjusted R^2 of 0.918 showed that about 92 % of variation in the dependent variable (AGDP) is explained by the independent variables. In Nigeria, arable land, exchange rate and consumer price index significantly affect domestic food production. Generally, in Nigeria, domestic food production has been decreasing while food import has been increasing making the country to be food import dependent and one that cannot feed itself.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of the study the following recommendations are made.

- i. Vast uncultivated land in the rural areas should be cultivated. This can be done through special incentives (free agricultural grants, modern agricultural equipment, processing and storage facilities) to the youths who involve in agriculture in the rural areas. This will encourage optimal cultivation of vast uncultivated arable land

and discourage rural- urban migration.

- ii. Exchange rate has been identified as a significant determinant of domestic food production, as many agricultural inputs have been imported. Production of domestic agricultural inputs should, therefore, be encouraged through domestic industries. This, in turn, will bring about decrease in importation of agricultural inputs, thus reducing the influence of exchange rate on agricultural production.

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